

RETRANSLATION AS THEORETICAL-PRACTICAL INTERROGATION ON EMINESCU'S TRADUCTOLOGY

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The need of retranslations and original contribution of each generation is a factor of renewing the national patrimony of each culture. The translations of dedicated authors, as the case Eminescu's opera, contribute to the deep revolution of all aesthetic norms in force in their literary space and play an essential role in the process of cultural space convergence.

The researcher Miroslava Metleaeva appreciates in her work the artistic aspect of the previous translations of the poetry "Luceafarul", their merits and deficiencies firstly, and the preservation of original text spirit and the transmission of the auctorial idea sense. The request of the translator Miroslava Metleaeva has deepened the existing translations by creating her own version and a freedom of increased creation. Her act of creation has followed the decoding of Eminescu's philosophical implications and the assignment of strong identity color of the original.

The personal special quality retranslation of Miroslava Metleaeva inscribes in the logics of *moving forward by overcoming* of Hegel and the *representation-supplement* (according to Gadamer), as the *identity* of translations relies on *alterity*, and its bicultural nature shows two modes of being and the intercultural relations between them.

Keywords: Traductology, literary translation, retranslation, Eminescu, decoding.

RETRADUCEREA CA INTEROGARE TEORETICO-PRACTICĂ ASUPRA TRADUCTOLOGIEI EMINESCIENE

Necesitatea retraducerilor și a contribuției originale a fiecărei generații este un factor de înnoire a patrimoniului național al fiecărei culturi. Traducerile autorilor consacrați, cum este cazul operei eminesciene, contribuie la revoluționarea în profunzime a tuturor normelor estetice în vigoare în spațiul lor literar și joacă un rol esențial în procesul de convergență a spațiilor culturale.

Cercetătoarea Miroslava Metleaeva evaluează în lucrarea sa latura artistică a traducerilor precedente ale poemului „Luceafărul”, a meritelor și deficiențelor lor estetice, în primul rând, dar și respectarea spiritului textului original și transmiterea sensului ideii auctoriale. Demersul traducătoarei Miroslava Metleaeva a aprofundat traducerile existente prin crearea propriei versiuni și o mai multă libertate de creație. Actul său de creație a urmat decodarea implicațiilor filozofice eminesciene și atribuirea unei inedite identități a originalului.

Retraducerea personală de o calitate deosebită a Miroslavei Metleaeva se înscrie în logica *depășire ca progres înainte* lui Hegel și a *reprezentări-suplinire* (după Gadamer), întrucât *identitatea* traducerii are la bază *alteritatea*, iar natura sa biculturală demonstrează că este vorba de două moduri de a fi și de relația interculturală dintre ele.

Cuvinte-cheie: traductologie, traducere literară, retraducere, Eminescu, decodare.

The circulation of culture and civilization values, covered by translated books, in time and space, is a factor of renewing the national patrimony of each culture, the translation being an absolute necessity, their contribution to the modernization and universalization of ideas and languages being considerable, as Heliade Radulescu mentioned when he was initiating a wide program of literary translation in/from Romanian language at the beginning of 19th century. Pascale Casanova remarked in her volume *The World Republic of Letters*: "The translation is the high authority of language's specific consecration of the literary universe. (...) it is (...) a form of literary recognition and not only a change of language, a simple horizontal exchange and it is equivalent to the achievement of literary certificate" [1, p. 172, 174].

The translation is the field that may assert the unique and original expression of a nation. The other country's literature discovers also by the translating its top creations. When our creations will be adequately translated, we will enter the international circuit. The list of creations to translate (if there is an appropriate eventual program as the one Heliade Radulescu mentioned) has to start inevitably with Eminescu. The faith of his creations translations makes history and became tradition in our space, due to the translators' efforts and the interpretations conducted by the distinctive academician Mihai Cimpoi toward which, year by year, converge the efforts of Eminescu's creations researchers from the entire world, including those that make translations.

The magisterial request of Miroslava Metleaeva (Luchiancicova) work "Interpreting the translations of Eminescu's *Luceafarul* in Russian language" [2, p. 237] is to conceive the translation as part and inevitable prolongation of the literature. For our translator and interpreter, the literature is not constituted only of unique creations, but also of the amount of translations, the literature being therefore as evidence of translation. The dialogue of translation with the literature is related to the permanent confrontation of the language and literature ideologies with the historical functioning of literature.

Therefore, a culture becomes universal by translations, and the "act of translation is co-substantial to the culture as act, within act" [3, p. 271]. The mechanisms of translation impose as being isomorphs with those of creation, declared Irina Mavrodin, one of the top translators from French into Romanian. The text arises from the imagination of the poet and lives in other languages by the imagination of the translator. Very interesting seems to be the statement of Miroslava Luchiancicova about the resemblance and the differentiation of the creative imagination of the author and the translation. Having in both cases, the active character of the creative imagination, the author will note the differential peculiarities: independence, novelty and originality of images and ideas of author, and the evocative character of the imagination in the case of translator.

The case of more translators and literary critics concurrently, as the one of Irina Mavrodin, Emil Iordache and Miroslava Metleaeva, is the one of interpretation and translation as form of experience in the sense that every translation is itself an interpretation. It includes all openings, foundations and levels of interpretation; the interpretation is no more, in its turn, than the realization of the translation. We consider that the work of Miroslava Metleaeva is a theoretical-practical interrogation on the poetical activity.

The knowledge and the application of the theoretical support from the national and international space allows to the author to set up for and to verify her own researches. Complementary to the directions and to analyzed doctrines, we may say that the work meets some theories of translations as: *Translation as consubstantial act of artistic creation* (R. Jakobson), *Translation as adventure of the imaginary* (J. Burgos), *Translation as adventure of the style* (E. Cioran), *Translation as possibility by compromise* (S. Marcus), *Translation as mean of accumulation, and redistribution of symbolic capital* (M. Jeanrenaud), the las being analyzed by Miroslava Luchiancicova from another perspective.

If in case of non-literary translations we rely on the use of specialized terminologies and some techniques greatly dedicated, then in case of literary translation, we talk about quasi-impossibility to express in another language the singularity of the artistic text, which is the quicksilver difficult to catch and to fix. What we understand better through the work of Miroslava Metleaeva that what is more difficult to preserve in a work, is the native cultural substrate, which gives to the text a strong identity color. In translations, the perfect knowledge of the two languages – the one of the original and the one of the translation – is doubled by a deep penetration of the translated work microcosm

and the microcosm civilization of it. The translation is a metalanguage, a method to describe another symbolic system, the cultural one. Henri Meschonnic has concluded eloquently: “pretending to translate only the language, culture was therefore translated”.

The local perspective addressed to a foreign public implies each time unique as sense and form innovations and transfers. This report, really special between content and form, osmosis in which sometimes the form becomes content, makes some critics, as G. Genette for example, be skeptical as for the translation of the poetry and treat untranslatability as evidence of authenticity and value of the poetical text. Detaching from this controversial postulate, Miroslava Metleaeva will rely on the great works of Eugen Coseriu, which are pertinent in this case. Miroslava Metleaeva makes clear and understood her position, defining the main purpose of the translation as transmission of the auctorial idea sense, respecting as faithful as possible the artistic peculiarities of the original and without alienating from the text original.

We are living in a world deploying an intensive activity of translation in different fields, “the literary ones being the most hurried and, often, many of them are approximate as language, as fidelity toward original and toward the requirements of literary work esthetic expression, in which the style is capital, demanding from translator competence” [4, p. 215], passion and talent. Hence, it is necessary of retranslations and original contribution of each generations, factor of renewing the national patrimony of each culture. The translations of dedicated authors, as the case of Eminescu’s creations, contribute to the deep revolution of all esthetic norms in force in their literary space and play an essential role in the convergence process of cultural spaces.

The retranslation relates to the transposition of the original message at a certain moment in a specific context, as “the literary translation appears therefore as a series always open, as an activity always restarted, never ended, definitive” [5], remaining as open work for other generations. No poetry is susceptible to be translated just once, as it is not passible of a single lecture. We will ascertain the original contribution of each generation favoring the neologisms, which sometimes reveals vintage terms in order to catch certain lost yet unperceived senses. It is the request of translator Miroslava Metleaeva, who, in new times, has deepened the existing translations by creating her own version, has proved more freedom of creation (according to the theorems of J.-R. Ladmiral, the translator is convicted to be free). Her act of creation, beyond the surface of words, has followed the decoding of Eminescu’s philosophic implications.

Surely, the translations meet the canons that monitor the original thinking of author not be distorted. Miroslava Metleaeva, for whom the canon is “a set of esthetic norms/criteria specific to a period”, “pursues the evolution of canonizing versions of the masterpiece in Russian language” [6, p. 21].

The literary translations and the specialized translations commit the expression to a faithful conformity toward the construction and the style of the foreign message, and appeal, unlike the non-literary translations, the imagination of the translator to recreate the sense in the language of translation.

What Miroslava Metleaeva analyzes in her work the appreciation of artistic side of previously translated poetry “Luceafarul”, their esthetic merits and deficiencies, firstly, and the preservation of the original text spirit. The mission of Miroslava Metleaeva as translator appears as intellectual duty to synthetize the translations and their different fundamental criteria and values.

Greatly, the work of Miroslava Metleaeva is the appreciation of previous translations, by invoking the traductology criteria based on signification and equivalence, ethics and fidelity’s controversy and others, supposing a certain respect for original and readers.

The recreation of Eminescu's text by Miroslava Metleaeva is the testimony of an affective intelligence and selective one, a given probably native, and mainly, cultivated of what will make her translation memorable. This success is very important for the re-appreciation of existing translations, and for the deep comprehension of Eminescu's literary creation. The comparison with other versions and the comment of own creative effort has highlighted the limits and the successes of her predecessors (M. Mirimski and Iu. Kojevnikov, Grigore Perov, Alexandru Brodski and David Samoilov), and her own researches and completions. The failures of predecessors are related to the disrespect of registers, gender restraints, heterogeneousness of styles, auctorial presence, simplification of imagistic system and others. The legitimacy of translation resonates with the original's text.

In *How to integrate/ Cum ne integrăm*, a speech given at the meeting of Romanian writers from the entire world, Arcadie Suceveanu has ascertained that has success in translation the person who, as in poetry, passes through the metaphysical zones, uprising the verbal material in the transcendental space of logosphere. Obviously, the essence and the purpose of the poetical translation, and literary one in general, do not reduce to render the sense, they have to achieve the equivalences semantically and stylistically in order to produce on the reader the same effect. The process of translation supposes the divergent interpretation of the sense, polysemy, ambiguity, losses, inappropriate reception. This fact explains why almost every translation may be considered simultaneously a relative success and a relative failure. The Indian writer of English language Salman Rushdie has specified in *Imaginary homelands/ Patrii imaginare*: "It is admitted, generally, that translating means to lose something; I stick stubbornly to the idea that translating means also to earn something" [7, p. 28]. The second part answers by a very explicit analyzes of this retroactive lecture. Hence, when Miroslava Metleaeva emphasizes the problem of different literary dominant, which give birth to creation sample, I would insist more on the report of inevitable *divergence* than the conflictual one used in the work (situation-limit not always achieved), as we consider that the mission of the translator consists in overpassing this situation of divergence through the equilibration and harmonization brought in the translation itself.

It is considered that the translation is never definitive, it is open by its nature and by the need at each passing of time to have an adequate variant. From here arises the need of retranslating. We will quote here Paul Valery: "The work lasts as long as it is capable to appear different from the one the author created".

The personal special quality retranslation of Miroslava Metleaeva inscribes in the logics of *moving forward by overcoming* of Hegel and the *representation-supplement* (according to Gadamer), as the *identity* of translations relies on *alterity*, and its bicultural nature shows two modes of being and the intercultural relations between them.

The current traductology recognizes the fact in translation the report establishes between two concept systems and not only between two languages (v. Simona Pollicino and others). Therefore, "the translator is firstly a reader decoding and analyzing the message from source language and subsequently a writer re-codifying it and restructuring it in the target language" [8, p. 65]. Mavrodin Irina testified also that she deconstructs and then she builds [9, p. 125]. In the concept of French sinologist Francois Julien to translate means to declassify in order to reclassify. Miroslava Metleaeva manages to inscribe this request in this logic, being aware that "almost every word in the poetry is codified and all comprehension issues of auctorial idea are tightly related to decoding the sense and the precedence of the text" [6, p. 21].

If a translation has to be periodically rethought, reviewed, rearranged, it is not for the fact that its author may be brought to the transfiguration of certain features, remarks the poet and Belgian

translator Fernand Verhesen, as the original text, by an independent movement of space and time, is the generator of own becoming [10, p.18]. Fernand Verhesen will add that the process of creation-recreation in translation has to be overpassed the subjectivity (introspective method to which refers Miroslava Metleaeva in the favor of a paradoxical objectivity). The poet-translator will highlight that the translator is put in the situation of conflict division between own individuality and Alter one. The resolution of this conflict implies the text in a route in which the divergent parts intercross in order to dialogize creatively. It is an important conclusion of the work. The act of translation situates at the crossroad of different identities. In order to equilibrate this inter-subjective space, in which the translator has the impression of de-personalization, he/she comes to release himself/herself of distortion shell. The translator has to put in brackets own cultural baggage in order to favour the concept freedom of Other, and passing through all these meanders of translation, he/she configures finally a new scene, a new space [*ibidem*, p. 23, 27].

Therefore, we conclude that the work contributes meritoriously to what we would call the rehabilitation of translator. The modesty (coming from the double hypostases in which is Miroslava Metleaeva) did not allow to emphasize entirely the plusvalue of own translation consisting of very adequate retranscription of Eminescu's thinking intensity, the perception of imagistic ensemble, the adaptation of language elements, *realias* and *culturems* of another culture, the maintenance of rhythm and melos, the empathy of cultures and others. Responding to a new horizon of expecting the current receiver, for Miroslava Metleaeva the translation has nothing to do with Babylonian curst traditionally invoked, it became for her *a modus vivendi, sentendi, parlandi*.

We believe that the work of Miroslava Metleaeva has the potential of quality translation in order to function as individual work, ideal toward still aspirates Quintilian.

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